

RM ROADMAP

Consensus Document for Country Community PORTUGAL

Co-Creation Session 2: Who are research managers/ skills and competences

Ambassador(s): Luis Silva, Tatiana Lima Costa

Associate Ambassador(s): Cláudia Barbosa, Mariana Santa-Marta

Authors: Tatiana Lima Costa, Cláudia Barbosa, Mariana Santa-Marta, Luis Silva

May 2024

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.

RM ROADMAP

“Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen the European Research Area”

Funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme

Consensus Document Country Community PORTUGAL

Co-Creation Session 2: Who are research managers/ skills and competences

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.

Co-Creation Session 2

Who are research managers/ skills and competences

Contents

1. Introduction	4
2. Summary of Co-Creation Session 2	6
3. Acknowledgments	29

1. Introduction

This is an important moment for the research management (RM) community in Europe. The European Commission (EC) and countries across Europe want to better understand the current research management landscape to further strengthen the European Research Area (ERA).

Research management includes a broad range of professionals supporting researchers to achieve excellence in research and in translation of the respective results. For the purpose of this co-creation exercise, Research Managers (RMs) are to be considered as broad as possible including: research policy advisers, research managers, financial support staff, data stewards, research infrastructure operators, knowledge transfer officers, business developers, technology transfer managers, innovation managers, etc. For simplicity, we use the term research management but this exercise covers also other terms such as research support, research management and administration, professionals at the interface of science and other terms which are used as the norm in the national landscapes across Europe.

The RM Roadmap Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP) brings research managers together to shape the future of the profession and support the strengthening of an inclusive research management community in Europe. The KCP is a place where research managers share their views and introduce issues for discussion in a solution-focused endeavour. RM Roadmap Ambassadors lead the discussions for each country on the Knowledge and Community Platform, supported by national and regional RM networks.

This co-creation exercise is the biggest collaboration between RM networks ever to take place in Europe. With a focus on learning insights from RMs, the co-creation exercise seeks to establish a robust framework that can support professional growth and collaboration across the EU and associated countries.

By 2023, 40 country communities have been established within the RM Roadmap Ambassador Network.

These have been complemented by 10 thematic communities, including 35 additional Ambassadors on top of the 114 national Ambassadors at the beginning of 2024. The RM Roadmap project will use the outcomes from this co-creation exercise to make a roadmap

for the future of research management in Europe and to build and exchange solid knowledge on career framework opportunities, upskilling and networking for research managers. RM Roadmap will ultimately build a value proposition for policy makers and institutional leaders who want to strengthen and modernise their research support departments.

This **consensus document for Country Community PORTUGAL** contains the outcomes of the **Second Co-Creation Session – Who are research managers/ skills and competences**.

A short summary of the main outcomes from the co-creation exercise is included in section 2. More information about the topic of research managers/ skills and competences is detailed in section 3.

For more information about the RM Roadmap initiative, the reader can consult the following website: www.rmroadmap.eu

2. Summary of Co-Creation Session 2

The second co-creation session of the RM Roadmap project took place between April 2nd to May 7th.

This second co-creation event fostered a consensus on a unified perception of the research management profession across Europe through the establishment of a shared and harmonized definition and terminology applicable across the diverse spectrum of roles within the profession. Notably, this consensus-building process was informed by a survey conducted between November 2023 and January 2024, which sought to delineate the identities of research managers, identify their core competencies, and pinpoint any overlooked facets. Additionally, the session aimed to compile pertinent national data and insights to enrich the analysis of individual country outcomes, thus facilitating a comprehensive understanding of the profession's complex landscape.

During the second co-creation session and building upon the experience of the first co-creation session and the RM Roadmap Ambassador's meeting that took place in Lisbon on March 13th, the PT Ambassadors implemented a novel complementary strategy to enhance engagement with the Portuguese Research Management community.

The 2nd co-creation session was launched by the project on the platform and, following the session's launch, the Ambassadors devised an online form mirroring the EARMA RM Roadmap 2nd co-creation session to solicit feedback from the national community. This form was disseminated via various channels, including the national RMA network ("Plataforma de Interface à Ciência", PIC) mailing list - encompassing over 800 Research Managers, personalized emails, LinkedIn, and Facebook, to inform and mobilize the Portuguese community for active participation.

RM-ROADMAP 2nd co-creation session – Who are Research Managers/Skills and Competences - PORTUGAL

RM ROADMAP aims to create a **consensus on the understanding of the Research Management (RM) profession** and **propose a working definition and terminology for the profession**, both at large and for specific categories.

The RM Roadmap survey, which collected inputs between 2 November 2023 and 28 January 2024, included specific questions designed to provide evidence from the RM community in all countries of the European Research Area on the current status, position and needs of research managers.

By relying on the outcome of the survey, the **upcoming co-creation sessions aims to validate and expand the survey results** with the national and thematic RM communities, and to shape these results with specificities reflecting the **various national contexts**.

The following areas are concerned in the second co-creation session:

- **Who are research managers?**
- **What are their key skills & competences?**

The session aims to gather feedback and validation from the national and thematic communities with two aims:

- first, to **identify any potential gaps or missing aspects**,
- second, to **gather evidence about any national circumstances** that may be relevant when applying the results at the national levels

The Portuguese (Co)Ambassadors: Tatiana Costa, Luís Silva, Cláudia Barbosa, Mariana Santa-Marta.

For any questions regarding the survey or data protection, please contact Cláudia Barbosa (cbarbosa@av.it.pt).

Seguinte

Concurrently, and in collaboration with PIC, the PT Ambassadors organized a *'Café com Ciência'* event” an online community gathering event hosted by PIC. This event was held on 30th April 2024, and the Ambassadors seized the opportunity to: introduce the RM Roadmap project; share insights from the 1st co-creation session; and engage with attendees on the evolving outcomes of the ongoing 2nd co-creation session to solidify community perspectives. During the meeting, the Ambassadors used several functionalities of the Zoom platform to promote interaction between the participants: a whiteboard for live feedback, a pool for voting, and a chat box also for live feedback. Participants also had the chance to do live comments and intervene.

A presentation slide for an online event. It features the RM ROADMAP logo at the top left, the EU funding banner at the top right, and a graphic of the Portuguese flag at the bottom right. The main text reads: "Who are research managers: skills and competences" followed by "Feedback da 2ª sessão de co-criação do projeto ROADMAP [a perspectiva nacional]". At the bottom left, it lists the organizers: "Cláudia Barbosa, Luís Silva, Mariana Santa-Marta, Tatiana Costa", the event name "Café com Ciência", and the date "30 Abril 2024". On the right side of the slide, there is a vertical column of small video thumbnails showing participants in a virtual meeting.

The event received positive feedback from the attendees, indicating a successful outreach and collaborative engagement approach.

No replies were found on the platform for the RM PT community. Using the cited approach and strategy, the Ambassadors collected 34 replies through the online form and detailed feedback and concrete suggestions/comments from the 62 RMAs at the “Café com Ciência” online event.

Discussion Outcomes of Co-Creation Session 2

This consensus document for Country Community **Portugal** contains the outcomes of the Second Co-Creation Session – Who are research managers/ skills and competences?

Q1: Respondents of the RM ROADMAP survey indicated the following areas in which they work (multiple selection was possible). (data from 28 January 2023, n=1851)

Q1.1: Do you miss any particular and/or emerging areas which should be also included in the definition of research management at the European level? If yes, please share!

The respondents from the Portuguese community identified a gap in roles pertaining to impact assessment, legal affairs, and human resources/team management. A discussion was generated about the legal/judicial roles: some respondents informed that their institutions had independent legal teams; others mentioned that in their teams they had colleagues with training in Law who, because of this background, were the ones responsible for analysing legal contracts among other documents; while others mentioned that an initial legal analysis is part of their (RMA) role. It was mentioned that specialized legal support for research and innovation could be exactly one area to develop within Science Management. It is currently very difficult to find professionals exclusively dedicated to this, but who knows, it could be a profession of the future.

It was also mentioned that the BESTPRAC project already had a working group dedicated to legal issues (still with a very low number of participants), with colleagues who already saw

themselves as science managers with this expertise of their own.

Q1.2: Are there any national specificities, e.g. certain areas being underdeveloped / non-existent, that influence the areas covered by research management? If yes, please elaborate on these factors and how they might affect the definition of research management at the national level.

One of the tendencies that could be noted from the answers collected was that specificities of the Portuguese community had much more to do with the way the Portuguese RMAs look at themselves (and perceive their identity) and the way the ecosystem understands RMAs, rather than specific areas being underdeveloped. Per se, this is an interesting outcome, as it seems to indicate that indeed the Portuguese community needs a more concrete definition to consolidate itself (and this will, in a reverse way, influence the areas covered by research management). In fact, the respondents pointed out that:

- "Several specific functions are not considered as research management but as administrative functions (e.g. project support regarding the financial part of it);
- "Other functions are not considered research management (e.g. for research data and information are often in the group of informatic technicians and library services, research ethics and integrity are closer);
- "Professionals identify themselves in other clusters/professional categories"
- "Research managers mainly identify themselves as research managers if they work in pre-award, post-award (not financial part), science communication and science-industry interface."

Also (and somehow probably influencing the above view/understanding), it appears that the profession and roles of Portuguese RMAs are, on one hand siloed (e.g. budget validation or administrative tasks) and on the other not integrated into all phases of the process (from ideation to implementation and post-evaluation?) or, contradictorily, fall into the "one-person-does-it-all" situation:

- "The profession is not integrated into all processes (e.g. little involvement of research managers in the development of proposals, mostly is only at the level of the budget)"
- "The technology transfer / applied research affects somehow the definition of these professionals and undermines the possible offer of training for these professionals"
- "It is possible for many RMs to develop their work through (and simultaneously with)

some of the above areas”.

- *“Many of these areas are developed (or managed) by the same project manager”*
- *“The Portuguese national policy towards scientific employment determines a wide range of decisions concerning recruitment and permanence of research staff and raises critical issues to research teams' management. More and more research managers are required to anticipate such critical points and to support researchers in diverse tasks, such as career planning (to ensure sequential approval of projects that can guarantee the researchers' salaries); team management (many researchers have been funded exclusively via individual programmes - ex. MSCA, CEEC - and have mainly worked by themselves, with little experience of collective work or team management and require great practical support, beyond institutional policies in place, to manage conflict, disagreement and supervision roles)”*

Answers collected also mentioned as bottleneck the inexistence of a concrete framework to define RMA, the lack of policies and strategies regarding RMA at the institutional level, and the lack of recognition and valorization of the profession:

- *“No framework to define what an RMA is, as such there is little consensus on the areas and profiles that contribute to this role”;*
- *“The level of implementation of research management is still very weak in most institutions”*
- *“Lack of valorization and recognition of the profession”*
- *“Lack of understanding of the possible (individual) roles, job description and responsibilities”*

Some participants identified areas that are underdeveloped, such as *“Research Impact”* or *“Public regulations for procurement* but did not detail how this would be a Portuguese specificity or how this would influence the areas covered by research management in Portugal.

Q2: Respondents of the RM ROADMAP survey were asked to select the 3 most suitable professional titles with which they identify and could be used as umbrella/collective term at European level for RMs. The 5 most popular choices are as follows

Q2.1: Given the broad range of fields covered by research managers, what would be the most proper umbrella/collective term to be used at European level? Please pick one! The term should be embraced by professionals working in RM and understood by stakeholders of the R&I ecosystem including institution leaders, decision-makers, and policymakers.

The Portuguese Community was asked to vote on the most proper umbrella/collective term to be used at the European level. Our online survey respondents (n=40) voted as follows (with “research advisor” receiving no votes): *Research Manager and Administrator*, 47.5% (n=19); *Research Manager*, 30% (n=12); *Research Management and Support Professional*, 17.5% (n=7); *Research Support Professional*, 5% (n=2).

During the meeting, after an initial discussion with the attendees for the best umbrella definition that also fits the Portuguese language, the four options and the votes of national participants of the survey were presented. From 47 meeting participants who have accessed the quiz, **69%** (n=24) selected *Research Manager*, and **31%** (n=11) elected *Research Manager and Administrator*, effectively reversing the top two choices from the community. It is interesting to note that, during this exercise, the Portuguese community did not make any reference to the term “Professionals at the Interface of Science”, a term that also appears in literature^{1,2,3}. This can be explained by the fact that the term was not one of the top 5 voted terms which appears to implicate that the term is not widely recognized. On the other hand, it could have been expected that this discussion would be raised at the *Café com Ciência*, as it is a term initially proposed by the PT community⁴ and somehow (or expectedly) a

¹ Santos, J. M. R. C. A., Varela, C and Kerridge, Simon (2021) Professionals at the interface of science: is there more than meets the eye? Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education . ISSN 1360-3108.

² Agostinho, M., Moniz Alves, C., Aresta, S., Borrego, F., Borlido-Santos, J., Cortez, J., ... Vidal, S. (2020). The interface of science: the case for a broader definition of research management. *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 24(1), 19–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603108.2018.1543215>

³ Santos, J. M. R. C. A., Varela, C and Kerridge, Simon (2023), *Who are the Professionals at the Interface of Science Working at Research Funding, Science Policy Making, and Similar Organisations?*, <https://www.srainternational.org/blogs/srai-jra2/2023/10/18/who-are-the-professionals-at-the-interface-of-science>

⁴ Agostinho, M., Moniz Alves, C., Aresta, S., Borrego, F., Borlido-Santos, J., Cortez, J., ... Vidal, S. (2020). The interface of science: the case for a broader definition of research management. *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 24(1), 19–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603108.2018.1543215>

particularity of the community (e.g. The PT informal network is named “*Plataforma de Interface à Ciência*”).

In the section below the initial comments on the survey vote (n=41) can be found, also considering a translation into Portuguese and possible bias.

Q2.2: Please elaborate any specificities that may influence your choice given your national/regional context.

Several survey participants provided feedback on their choice, either by highlighting why the selected denomination was better or by indicating why the ones not selected were not a good choice. Answers (quoted as they were submitted) are presented for each denomination / umbrella term.

Research Manager and Administrator

- *RM deal with a wide variety of tasks, from routine management tasks to strategic planning. In either case, tasks are developed with increasingly greater autonomy and touch upon key areas for their institutions: funding, compliance, HR management. **The projectification of science, and an increasing dependency on individual-based funding (national scientific employment policies), have expanded the level of responsibility of RM and the impact of their work on institutions.** In this scenario, the RM often becomes a key player in the administration/management of R&D institutions, well beyond the scope of the project or the research group.*
- *It includes most of the RMA activities. Personally, I am also supporting researchers with deliverables, milestones, impact, writing specific information for call etc. Post-award: hiring process, all reports.*
- ***I believe it is the most comprehensive, considering that Portugal has few job specifications.***
- ***All the terms are appropriate** and can be used to define the profession. Depending on professionals' functionalities and roles in their institutions, one term may be more suitable than the others. **I chose RMA because professionals must be able to carry out a wide range of tasks that include proper management of research activities***

and day-to-day administrative tasks that include other administrative areas of organizational management.

- *I feel that the term captures the role and **grants it some "authoritativeness": as it stands we are not recognized as experts on a particular field, just administrative/clerical staff** that, for the most of time, is seen as "playing it by ear" rather than being experts.*
- *It seems to me that the professional title "Research Manager and Administrator" would be the most appropriate term, given the **range of fields covered, which can range from all kinds of administrative support to managing calls for projects and research data and outputs, science communication, among others.***
- *Reflection of the responsibilities of the position.*
- ***Most of the time we do more than research managing, being till a certain point advisors/administrators.***
- *I miss the word Innovation.*
- ***Managers and Administrators have different conceptualisations in EU and USA. Having both expressed in the designation may be helpful to easily include all the tasks performed in the career.***

Research Manager

- ***Research advisor is seen as a more senior position. All the other designations reduce our profession to bureaucratic work.***
- ***Administrator in Portugal is more related to a CEO kind of like position. Does not make sense. Support professional I believe that brings no added value to the name of the position and we are not simply advisers. We implement actual work.***
- *I hesitated between the first two hypotheses, but the second best summarises the function, not least because the **term administrator ends up being redundant***
- *I would choose project manager for my specific case, considering the scope of my activities - technical delivery in industry partnership, which includes some budget control, team management and hiring, contract revision, and, barely any contribution to scientific output (peer-reviewed publications).*
- *A research manager is not an administrator. In my opinion, an administrator is at a higher*

level than the research manager, which can be coordinated by the administrator.

- *I think Research Manager covers a broader spectrum of activities*
- *I believe the term must be as broad as possible.*
- ***As a Portuguese, I believe that a research manager is the most comprehensive to encompass several areas***
- *I believe it is more general and covers more the larger spectrum of roles.*
- ***Broad enough to cover the different areas without the bias of the "only" admin.***

Research Management and Support Professional

- ***The term Research Manager may restrict the functions of a professional to management tasks.*** *In reality, these professionals often not only manage but also provide training and actively contribute to research projects. Therefore, I believe it is more comprehensive to also consider them as support.*
- *Within the specific elements of the areas of activity, **the term support would be a correct definition, together with the term research management. However, a more concise and focused name would be more meaningful and easier to identify.***
- *It's a complex definition with a challenging conclusion.*
- *The term should have the following characteristics: captures all the dimensions in which an RM works; comprehensive enough; identifiable and objective.*
- *It seems to me the most similar to the functions.*
- *Research Management is appropriate in my opinion, without the "Support Professional" it is not clear to me what it means.*
- *In my opinion, a research manager seems to understand the science/research that we are managing. In the other side, Research management is more broad, is about management and not research.*

Research Support Professional

- *I think it is hard for the external people to understand the concept of Research Manager... On the other side, the **concept of support is more easily understandable.** Nevertheless, the concept of Research Manager is already entering into the people ears... would not be good to change that... so... hard to decide!*

After presenting all the general initial results (RMA 47% vs RM 30%) one of the attendees asked the community: *What do you think would be the best translation for RMA into Portuguese so that it can be integrated into a Portuguese career?*

This question triggered a discussion on the specificities of the presented terms and the options at hand for the national landscape and for the national professional: we could have a different and specific name for Portugal (where the term “Gestor de Ciência e Tecnologia” seems to be the more consensual option), or, if the idea is to translate the umbrella term *Research Manager and Administrator*, special care should be given to the translation since the word *Administrator* in Portuguese might be confused either with CEOs and high-level positions at institutions or, on the opposite side of the spectrum, have connotations with exclusively administrative tasks (e.g. secretariat services).

Q3: The table outlines the most important skills and competences revealed by the RM ROADMAP survey for each of the identified areas of research management. Identification of these skills and competences for the different areas can help employers in recruitment, provide career paths and professional development opportunities for RMs, and articulate better the training needs. Are there additional skills or competences that should be included among the top 5 identified in the RM Roadmap survey for each area? If yes, please share your suggestions!

During the first auscultation stage, several survey participants provided feedback on this task, identifying additional skills that they considered to be missing from the tables. The answers mostly did not identify which type of skill (transversal; soft; hard, or role-specific) they referred to, which made it difficult to classify them categorically.

During the meeting, the Ambassadors presented the questionnaire results to the community highlighting that the skills identified by the RM Roadmap project for each role and area (transversal; soft; hard, or role-specific) were only the Top 5 skills (and not all for each role) and resulted from the questionnaire. Given the difficulty felt when assessing the responses previously, the Ambassadors further highlighted that the majority of the respondents, when identifying a “missing” top 5 skill, did not identify to which category the skill should be added and, as such, asked the meeting attendees to leave comments on the Zoom chat to allow a refined comment on the missing skills.

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.

Below are the original Top 5 skills and competencies identified by the RM Roadmap survey for each skill category. In **Purple**, the Portuguese Ambassadors added the skill and competencies identified by category and in black all other skills identified as “missing” top 5 by the Portuguese community.

	Transversal skills relevant for RMs	RM related soft skills	RM related hard skills	Specialisation or role related skills
RESEARCH STRATEGY AND POLICY DEVELOPMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Written communication • Oral communication • Problem solving • Self-motivation, proactiveness, initiation • Critical thinking • Clear communication • Proactivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritisation • Time management • Efficiency and effectiveness • Reliability, trustfulness • Planning, strategic thinking • pleasant, friendly; flexible, open-minded 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand research and the R&I ecosystem • Knowledge of rules and regulations of funders • Understanding institutional governance • Ethics, integrity • Language skills (EN) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appreciating values and understanding interests • Understanding politics and policy cycles • Building and maintaining networks • Stakeholder engagement and management • Administrative skills
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organizational skills • Openness to new cultures and backgrounds • Active listening • Empath communication • Proactive troubleshooting • Information management • Time management • Problem-solving 			
	Transversal skills relevant for RMs	RM related soft skills	RM related hard skills	Specialisation or role related skills
PROPOSAL DEVELOPMENT (PRE-AWARD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Written communication • Problem solving • Flexibility • Openness • Oral communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritisation • Adaptability • Time management • Reliability • Trustfulness • Active listening, Empathy • Proactive troubleshooting • Original (Creative), Innovative 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of rules and regulations of funders • Language skills (EN) • IT skills • Ethics, integrity • Understand research and the R&I ecosystem 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrative skills • Appreciating values and understanding interests • Building and maintaining networks • Financial skills • Understanding politics and policy cycles

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Proactivity ● Assertiveness 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Legal knowledge ● Organizational skills ● resilience, or resilience coaching ● openness to new cultures and backgrounds ● knowledge of impact mechanisms ● previous experience in R&D as a researcher ● Team management (proposal team) ● Budgeting and cost management ● Contract risks ● Creativity ● Prior experience in participating and managing projects ● Teamwork ● Team and stakeholder management (consortium building) ● Understand the impact evaluation of the projects 			
	Transversal skills relevant for RMs	RM related soft skills	RM related hard skills	Specialisation or role related skills
PROJECT SUPPORT (POST-AWARD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Written communication ● Oral communication ● Interpersonal skills ● Intrapersonal skills ● Flexibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Prioritisation ● Time management ● Information management ● Efficiency and effectiveness ● Reliability, trustfulness ● anticipate situations/problems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IT skills ● Ethics, integrity ● Knowledge of rules and regulations of funders ● Understand research and the R&I ecosystem ● Managing resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Administrative skills ● Financial skills ● Appreciating values and understanding interests ● Building and maintaining networks ● Legal and regulatory skills
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Accounting skills ● Organizational skills ● Conflict management ● Openness to new cultures and backgrounds 			

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Knowledge of impact mechanisms ● Accounting skills ● Language skills ● Problem-solving ● Cross-reference information ● Teamwork 			
	Transversal skills relevant for RMs	RM related soft skills	RM related hard skills	Specialisation or role related skills
TRANSLATION OF RESULTS: SCIENCE COMMUNICATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Flexibility ● Oral communication ● Interpersonal skills ● Self-motivation, proactiveness, initiation ● Problem solving ● Communication as a whole, not just oral 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Adaptability ● Prioritisation ● Time management ● Reliability, trustfulness ● Efficiency and effectiveness ● Original (creativity) ● Innovative 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Language skills (EN) ● IT skills ● Understand research and the R&I ecosystem ● Knowledge of rules and regulations of funders ● Ethics, integrity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Building and maintaining networks ● Appreciating values and understanding interests ● Understanding politics and policy cycles ● Stakeholder engagement and management ● Administrative skills
Missing skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Summarize and writing skills ● Cultural and diversity comprehensive skills ● Openness to new cultures and backgrounds ● Ability to translate complex themes into simple messages. ● Stakeholders' engagement. ● Creativity ● Empathy ● Some teaching skills ● Communication skills ● Assertiveness ● Information management ● Citizen & Science understanding ability ● Written communication 			

	Transversal skills relevant for RMs	RM related soft skills	RM related hard skills	Specialisation or role related skills
TRANSLATION OF RESULTS: UPTAKE AND UTILISATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oral communication • Problem solving • Interpersonal skills • Critical thinking • Assertiveness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritisation • Planning, strategic thinking • Time management • Information management • Adaptability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand research and the R&I ecosystem • Knowledge of rules and regulations of funders • Language skills (EN) • Management skills • Understanding institutional governance • Intersectoral knowledge • managing resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building and maintaining networks • Administrative skills • Stakeholder engagement and management • Financial skills • Legal and regulatory skills
Missing skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organizational skills • Openness to new cultures and backgrounds • Ability to translate complex themes into simple messages • Stakeholders engagement • Pro-activity • Entrepreneurship • Patents • Translate Science into Business • Translate Business to Academics • Understand the different models & channels of TT • Skills in the evaluation of the economic value of research results • Marketing • Negotiation 			
	Transversal skills relevant for RMs	RM related soft skills	RM related hard skills	Specialisation or role related skills
MANAGEMENT INFORMATION AND	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problem solving • Openness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptability • Stress management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrative skills

RELATED FUNCTIONS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Flexibility ● Cultural and diversity skills ● Interpersonal skills ● Attention to detail 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Resilience ● Time management ● Prioritisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Understanding institutional governance ● Knowledge of rules and regulations of funders ● Understand research and the R&I ecosystem ● Ethics and integrity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Appreciating values and understanding interests ● Financial skills ● Appreciating values and understanding interests ● Cross-cutting issues in HEU
Missing skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Organizational skills ● Communication Skills (oral and written) ● Data science, Big data management, Data privacy ● Information management ● Reports management 			
	Transversal skills relevant for RMs	RM related soft skills	RM related hard skills	Specialisation or role related skills
RESEARCH SUPPORT DELIVERY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Assertiveness ● Written communication skills ● Interpersonal skills ● Intrapersonal skills ● Oral communication skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Time management ● Prioritisation ● Adaptability ● Reliability, trustfulness ● Efficiency and effectiveness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Knowledge of rules and regulations of funders ● Language skills (EN) ● IT skills ● Understanding institutional governance ● Managing resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Administrative skills ● Appreciating values and understanding interests ● Financial skills ● Understanding politics and policy cycles ● Building and maintaining networks
Missing skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Organizational skills ● Stakeholders engagement ● Team management ● Conflict management ● People skills ● Mediation ● Multitasking ● Problem-solving 			

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Information management ● Ability to cross-reference information ● Teamwork 			
	Transversal skills relevant for RMs	RM related soft skills	RM related hard skills	Specialisation or role related skills
TRAINING, RESEARCHER DEVELOPMENT, POSTGRADUATE RESEARCHERS (PGR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Assertiveness ● Oral communication ● Written communication ● Openness ● Flexibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Adaptability ● Time management ● Reliability, trustfulness ● Working in teams ● Efficiency and effectiveness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Language skills (EN) ● Knowledge of rules and regulations of funders ● Ethics, integrity ● Understand research and the R&I ecosystem ● IT skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Administrative skills ● Building and maintaining networks ● Appreciating values and understanding interests ● Understanding politics and policy cycles ● Cross-cutting issues in HEU ● teaching skills
Missing skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Organizational skills ● Openness to new cultures and backgrounds ● Stakeholders' engagement ● Training skills ● Be always updated ● Interpersonal skills ● Intrapersonal skills (self-awareness of our strengths and weaknesses) ● Understand current needs of training and career development ● Teamwork 			
	Transversal skills relevant for RMs	RM related soft skills	RM related hard skills	Specialisation or role related skills
RESEARCH ETHICS AND INTEGRITY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Written communication ● Multitasking ● Interpersonal skills ● Cultural and diversity skills ● Openness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reliability, trustfulness ● Adaptability ● Time management ● Efficiency and effectiveness ● Planning, strategic thinking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ethics, integrity ● Language skills (EN) ● Knowledge of rules and regulations of funders ● Management skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Administrative skills ● Appreciating values and understanding interests ● Building and maintaining networks

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand research and the R&I ecosystem equity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder engagement and management Legal and regulatory skills
Missing skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organizational skills Openness to new cultures and backgrounds Awareness of Anti-bribery/corruption & conflict of interest, data protection policies Diplomatic, not complicated Legal knowledge Training skills 			
	Transversal skills relevant for RMs	RM related soft skills	RM related hard skills	Specialisation or role related skills
INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION, INSTITUTION BRANDING	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intrapersonal skills Flexibility Assertiveness Openness Critical thinking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reliability, trustfulness Stress management Time management Resilience Adaptability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IT skills Knowledge of rules and regulations of funders Understand research and the R&I ecosystem Understanding institutional governance Ethics, integrity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Appreciating values and understanding interests Lobbying Building and maintaining networks Administrative skills Understanding politics and policy cycles
Missing skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organizational skills Communication skills (oral and written) Availability Teamwork Openness to new cultures and backgrounds Language skills Cultural and diversity skills 			
	Transversal skills relevant for RMs	RM related soft skills	RM related hard skills	Specialisation or role related skills

COLLABORATION WITH INDUSTRY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural and diversity skills • Problem solving • Oral communication • Assertiveness • Openness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time management • Prioritisation • Planning, strategic thinking • Stress management • Working in teams 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding institutional governance • Knowledge of rules and regulations of funders • Management skills • Language skills (EN) • Managing resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building and maintaining networks • Administrative skills • Appreciating values and understanding interests • Nurturing innovation • Stakeholder engagement and management
Missing skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to translate complex themes into simple messages • Stakeholders' engagement • Communication skills • Results-oriented thinking • Interpersonal skills • Understand the different models & channels of TT • Skills in the evaluation of the economic value of research results • Strong negotiation skills • Negotiation 			
	Transversal skills relevant for RMs	RM related soft skills	RM related hard skills	Specialisation or role related skills
RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE MANAGEMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexibility • Openness • Written communication skills • Multitasking • Cultural and diversity skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teamwork • Stress management • Diplomatic skills • Conflict management • Time management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand research and the R&I ecosystem • Understanding institutional governance • IT skills • Language skills (EN) • Ethics, integrity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder engagement and management • Building and maintaining networks • Administrative skills • Understanding politics and policy cycles • Legal and regulatory skills • Financial skills
Missing skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information management • Team management • Capacity for multiple cross-cutting areas of knowledge 			

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data and resources management 			
	Transversal skills relevant for RMs	RM related soft skills	RM related hard skills	Specialisation or role related skills
RESEARCH DATA, RESEARCH INFORMATION, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY MANAGEMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assertiveness • Openness • Flexibility • Interpersonal skills • Oral communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptability • Negotiation • Time management • Conflict management • Reliability, trustfulness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand research and the R&I ecosystem • Knowledge of rules and regulations of funders • Understanding institutional governance • Management skills • Ethics, integrity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrative skills • Legal and regulatory skills • Building and maintaining networks • Understanding politics and policy cycles • Appreciating values and understanding interests
Missing skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness of Anti-bribery /corruption, conflict of interest, data protection policies & ethics • Proactivity • Creativity • Reports management • Problem-solving • Critical thinking • Strong skills and knowledge in IP 			

Discussion on this topic during the meeting started around the concept of “communication skills”: as communication skills are split and appear in the different tables as *written / oral / communication* skills, some RMAs did not understand why they were presented separately, and how to comprehend what is defined by each.

Another point of the discussion was related to the identified top 5 transversal skills relevant for RMAs: these are not consistent, and they should be – in end effect – transversal to all roles. **The community suggested that a consensus should be produced around the *Transversal skills* relevant to RMAs.** A further relevant comment was that some important skills appeared missing from the top 5, with a suggestion that it would probably be advisable to increase the number of skills.

There was also the **impression that the “*role-specific skills*” lists were not quite specific**, since, as a colleague pointed out *“for example, between “Translation of results - science communication” and “Translation of results - Uptake and Utilisation”, there are 3 specialised/role skills that are the same. If the goal is to provide a framework for career paths and help employers in recruitment, this will not allow them to distinguish between a science communicator and a knowledge transfer professional. Role skills should not be the same for different categories”*.

It was further noted that **some of the skills were “vague”**, as a participant pointed out: *“All categories include “administration skills” for instance, and that this type of skills may be detailed further and effectively specified for each role.”* A further participant stated to *“admit that the administration skills of a science communicator and a pre-award are not the same. Legal skills and financial skills will also not be the same depending on the category of RM”*

The community agreed that **there was a problem with the duplication of skills in the specialization role**, and also pointed out their disagreement with some of the top 5 skills. For example, including *“knowledge of rules and regulations of funders”* in the hard skills of science communicators is important if you are doing project communication, but there are probably other more relevant hard skills for a science communicator (doing and not doing project communication).

Globally, the Portuguese community considered this to have been a good exercise but thought that the results were inconclusive.

A fine-tuned exercise should be performed to: **avoid the duplication of skills in the specialization roles** (1 is ok, but 3 duplicated skills out of 5 is too much); take care in ensuring that **the skills are more specific** (or have a larger description); and **there is an agreement on the transversal skills between different roles**.

3. Acknowledgments

The Portuguese ambassadors would like to acknowledge the inputs of the Portuguese community, namely those who participated in the Café com Ciência or anonymously answered the online form, and in particular to: Ana Sofia Santiago, Petra Pintado, Inês Costa, Leonardo Veronez, Paulo Diogo Ferreira, Paula Soares, Marta Neto, Inês C. Rosa, Olga Karavai, Ana Tavares, Lara Franco, Filipa Carvalho, Sofia Aires Martins, Sara Correia, Regina Lencastre, Rita Rua Ferreira, Cristina Oliveira, Carolina Varela, Joana Costa, Sandra Aresta, Carla Pereira, Dina Carrilho.

RM ROADMAP

 rmroadmap.eu

 [@rmroadmap](https://twitter.com/rmroadmap)

 [linkedin.com/company/rmroadmap](https://www.linkedin.com/company/rmroadmap)

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.